

Virtual Communication: use, abuse and addictions in Social Networks.

Manuel Aguilar Yuste.

Doctor in Economics and Business from the University of Extremadura.
PhD. UEx. Spain.

Abstract.

Seventeen years ago that social networks entered the scene, first with Friendster and MySpace, then with Facebook in 2004; but it was not until the appearance and subsequent massification of smartphones between 2008 and 2010, that social networks became ubiquitous. Today we are talking about digital marketing, influencers, new business models based on big data and the number of "clicks", changes in social paradigms and new types of addiction. But, do we really understand what social networks are and how they affect us? Do we know its true scope? In this article, we will address the main issues of the digital world and we will know some of the possible interpretations that social networks cause in our lives, and it aims to discuss the causes and effects of addiction to social networks, the positive and negative consequences that result of addiction and analyzes the measures taken to stop all the effects that addiction brings in our daily lives.

Keywords: social networks, virtual Communication, digital addictions.

Introduction.

During recent years, there have been significant changes worldwide in terms of the quantitative and qualitative expansion of the Internet, social networks and the number of people who use them. Social networks are websites and applications or software that allow users to share content, opinions, ideas, beliefs, educational experiences, personal and social feelings. The most popular and used virtual social networks are Instagram, Telegram, Twitter, Skype, Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp and Snapchat.

The role and position of Communication through social networks in our society is playing a very important role in society, so much so that human beings are establishing new forms of Communication that are not even taught or regulated (Forero, 2011), of which, for example, Communication in general, and the language in particular of young people in the use of Social Networks, according to Rocha (2004), states that through chat you read what you want to read, not what is trying to be said. In a communicative

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context, in turn, it implies not only oral and written language, but other languages that, normally, are not taught to individuals because they are not within the norm, that is, the general pattern of society (Forero, 2011).

In the digital context, a social network is a platform that allows the interaction of “profiles” that represent people, brands, companies, organizations or causes in a virtual environment. Each of these platforms is designed to host and transmit certain types of content according to its function, use and target audience. Work networks, personal relationships, entertainment, financing, sports, cooking recipes. What they all have in common is multidirectional Communication between users and a specific digital environment. Currently, it is difficult to find a company, brand or person that does not have at least one personal profile on one of the most popular social networks. But are social networks as recent a phenomenon as we think?

Despite how “current” experiences such as Facebook, Instagram or LinkedIn may seem to us, social networks (RRSS) already existed long before the Internet was invented. A social network is a complex set of relationships built around common interests or objectives: social clubs, scientific societies, communities, guilds. Any group of people interested in the Communication of content through an exchange regulated by a few rules of mutual agreement can be considered a social network, although its natural place of insertion is an “off-line” environment, as Grapsas points out. (2017): “In sociology, for example, the social network has been used to analyze interactions between individuals, groups, organizations or even entire societies since the end of the 19th century.”

Over time, the evolution of social networks has changed the way companies relate to their audiences, as well as the type of “commercial pact” that both parties tacitly subscribe to. Pierre Laurent, director of the Waldorf of Peninsula school and former engineer at Microsoft, Intel and some other startups, says:

“(...) before, we wanted the user to be happy so that they would buy the product. Now (...) the business model is different: the product is free, but data is collected and advertisements are placed. Therefore, the goal today is for the user to spend more time in the application, to be able to collect more data or place more ads. That is to say, the purpose of the application is for the user to spend as much time as possible in front of the screen, they are designed for that.” (Guimon, 2019).

Evolution of Social Networks.

Nowadays, there are a huge number of social networks. Furthermore, social networks have become a paradigm, a flexible format of dynamic communications to which all

web applications or mobile terminals aspire. Creating a community on social networks is offering a set of functions that facilitates interaction between companies, brands and users, and guaranteeing direct accounting of the actions and reactions of users, without a doubt, is the best way to gain a space in the today's digital world. However, social networks have also evolved to specialize in content, niches and potential markets. Although websites are becoming more dynamic every day, the credibility of, for example, a brand in the digital world depends largely on the type of public “presence” that it manages to forge in the most popular social networks.

In addition to Facebook, some of the most important social networks today are:

- YouTube: created in 2005, it is the third social network used in Spain with 68%, according to the 2019 Annual Study of Social Networks (prepared by IAB Spain); specializes in online video storage and playback. Although many users consider it more of a social media tool, YouTube is a full-fledged social network: it allows you to register as a user and create a channel with a profile that can be customized and visited by other users, receive messages and comments. , have subscribers and subscribe to other channels, vote for or against videos and share content through third-party instant messaging and other social networks.

- Twitter: created in 2006, it is a microblogging service that offers plain text publications with a maximum of 280 characters (originally 140), with options to embed images (since 2011) and videos (since 2012). Used by 50% of Spaniards; This social network has a potentially enormous reach and interconnectivity: users can catalog messages through hash tags or hashtags ('#'), which makes each message visible in a specific context and creates thematic “trends” quantified in alive and monitorable by anyone. In addition, it allows you to make direct mentions of other users and create cross-talk between different profiles through public communication threads that can be traversed in all their dimensions.

- Instagram: it is currently the social network with the greatest growth (this year it went from 49% to 54% in the Spanish market) and is the favorite of the youngest. It was created in 2010 as an application for iPhones and we had to wait two years for the Android version to also appear. Instagram focuses on capturing, editing and publishing “snapshot” photos and videos. It allows you to find and follow close friends or famous personalities, brands, companies or people with similar content that we don't know. We can also create and follow hashtags, privileging thematic interests over individual relationships. In 2016, Instagram added a segment called Stories (a function modeled on the social network Snapchat) that allows you to upload photos and short videos, content that is played in sequence according to the order in which it is added, available only for 24 hours from the moment of upload. your publication. One of the main attractions of

this type of content is its daily registration invoice, which can be accompanied by editing templates, filters and stickers, text or music. Through “Stories”, Instagram allows you to make live videos, a function that has also been gaining space on other social networks.

- LinkedIn: founded in December 2002 and launched in May 2003, it is currently the largest professional network, with more than 250 million active users worldwide. As it focuses on labor and commercial relations, what we will find here will be companies and professionals seeking to promote themselves and create new strategic alliances. To register on this social network, the user only needs to fill out a form with data similar to what would be included in any resume: training, titles, past and current work experiences, skills, publications. Once the information provided is processed, LinkedIn explores and cross-references this data with billions of data stored and provided by other profiles. In a short time, potential connections related to the user will be shown that, on the one hand, will allow them to recover relationships lost over time and, on the other, open space in similar work scenarios not previously explored.

- WhatsApp: created in 2009 by Jan Koum, former Adobe and Apple employee, former director of the operations team at Yahoo! and former chief engineer to Brian Acton. To this day, there are conflicting opinions about whether WhatsApp is an instant messaging service or a social network. In Spain, it is the most used application, above all other social networks with 88%. In addition to sending and receiving text and audio messages and offering the option to send and receive images and documents, in WhatsApp – as in other social networks – the user has a profile in which they include personal information and a photo. In addition, users can communicate live through calls and video calls and, like Instagram and Snapchat, it has an editing interface that offers the possibility of modifying the images we send, adding texts, filters and emoticons. It has a segment called “status” very similar to Instagram, Facebook and Snapchat stories: photos, texts or videos played in sequence, only available for 24 hours. Allows you to create group chat rooms and broadcast lists of up to 256 people. Unlike other social networks, WhatsApp does not have a wall, board or billboard and the only way to find or add other people is through phone numbers.

Addiction to social networks.

Social media addiction is the compulsive use of social media or social media platforms for some personal reasons. Social media is mainly used for social purposes, such as maintaining some established offline networks, compared to individual ones. However,

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recent studies show that a person may feel obligated to maintain their online social networks in a way that can lead to excessive social media use.

Social networks can be a catalyst for maladaptive use, becoming sources of stress and anxiety, damaging the person's health, locking them in a depression of sadness, melancholy and absence of happiness; Furthermore, true clinical depression is a mood disorder in which feelings of sadness, loss, anger, or frustration interfere with daily life (Herrera, et al., 2010).

There have been many debates regarding behavioral addiction, whether any excessive behavior should be considered as genuine addictions such as video games, internet use or any other activity, the same debates continue around social media addiction. Some models Turel and Serenko (2012, cited in Griffiths et al., 2014) explain the formation of addiction to social networks, and this is:

I. The socio-cognitive model: this model, as Turel and Serenko (2012) point out, that abnormal social networks arise in the case of “the expectation of positive results, in combination with Internet self-concept and poor Internet self-regulation , eventually leads to compulsive or addictive social media behavior” (p 515-516).

II. Cognitive-behavioral model: This model emphasizes that abnormal social media occurs as a result of inadequate cognitions and is reinforced by environmental factors, and will ultimately lead to compulsive social media addiction.

III. Social Skills Model: This model, as noted by Griffiths et al. (2014), “people mostly lack self-presentation skills and therefore prefer virtual communication to face-to-face interactions and this eventually leads to compulsive addiction in using social media” (p. 123).

There are many reasons why social media is considered to be so addictive. This addiction affects different categories of people, such as adolescents, young adults and the elderly, but also social media addiction can be a result of education, mainly in research work and as a result of business, widely in marketing. Around personal relationships in society, people tend to become addicted to social media to alleviate conditions that occur to them such as fear of missing out (FOMO), this is mainly seen in teenagers. The fear of “missing out” is a big driver of social media use, as a large percentage fears not being aware of something that is happening in real time, whether it be their friends' posts, some daily news or maybe some live events on social media.

Ego is a big influence on social media addiction. We live in a society that shows that personal life, it is a "me" lifestyle. Many people will always want to be online, whether on Instagram or Facebook, just to receive live status updates of whatever they do.

People always compare themselves in evaluating feelings, strengths, weaknesses, abilities and even perspectives, and this will bring about social comparison and increased self-esteem.

Many people will feel good from a social validation point of view, in the sense that someone will feel good if they post a photo of themselves and get that 'Like' or even 'Favorite' from Facebook on the Twitter handle, this will make them repeatedly want to do this, and from there they will get into social media addiction.

Relevant desks in many companies use social media as marketing platforms (Priyadarshini et al, 2020). Department heads who care about online marketing will at some point be addicted to different platforms such as Facebook, to market their products or services and their brand. Social media is an essential piece of the business marketing strategy platform, helping with customer creation, new potential customers and sales, thereby increasing productivity.

Social media addiction is sometimes caused by the urge to escapism. Escapism is defined as a behavior used to distract oneself from real-life problems that can include depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem. For someone to escape from life's problems, they will need a feeling of participation in social networks and therefore the creation of the so-called "virtual world". If someone sees a lot of likes and comments on their posts, they will tend to think that other users care about them and, therefore, they will generate their own thought for each post.

Social anxiety seems positive for many people who struggle to maintain relationships or communicate in person, because online platforms provide the perfect environment for this. But it's not, due to the physical effects of excessive screen time and online consumption.

Social networks seem addictive for many of the users, because every day companies that develop applications mainly for Android use, update their programs to get better features for better and faster performance. This will make the user of a given app adapt to this by being eager to update their already installed apps to get better features.

In addition to the causes of addictions to social networks, there are also positive aspects of social networks in different ways, because among other issues, social networks bring people together, they bring together "virtual friends." Create a better network among many people who share similar interests and ambitions. It also raises awareness about important issues.

Addiction, at some level in our lives, brings emotional support during difficult times as it allows an environment to share our stories that affect us.

In relation to business, the addition of any marketing department of a given business brings a positive impact on the business's production in conversation, as it creates good customer service and user support, as well as customer engagement. and the audience.

Although some of the causes of social media addictions have positive effects on our daily lives, they also affect us negatively. There are many effects of addiction to social platforms, while some affect our health, business performance, and studies. Social media addiction has a great effect on the brain (Lewis, 2018), Internet addiction alters brain volume. The brain changes are similar to those produced by addiction to some drugs such as cocaine and alcohol. It decreases the gray and white matter fibers of the brain, which ultimately results in a change in emotional processing and functioning.

Addiction causes more depression and less well-being. Social media addictions linked to increased feelings of social isolation. We seem less happy when using social media platforms, for example, there is a case study of Facebook where it is linked to less happiness and life satisfaction from one moment to the next, where Facebook imports a perception of social isolation.

Comparing our lives to those of other users we encounter online is mentally unhealthy. Being addicted to online platforms will eventually lead us to the desire to want to live like others, this will lead to a false life and a tension about being who we are not.

Social media anxiety disorder is another case of mental health conditions, which are a result of social media addiction (Hoge et al., 2017). This phenomenon is beyond the fear of missing out. Some symptoms define social media anxiety disorder and these include:

- I. Feel like sharing a post online.
- II. Someone experiencing this disorder will have severe nervousness, anxiety, and discomfort from not checking social media platforms.
- III. In studies, some students will lose interest in schoolwork and other planned activities.
- IV. This disorder has a symptom of withdrawal from friends and family.
- V. In the middle of a conversation, someone will stop to check their phones.
- VI. Spending more than six hours a day mainly using social networks such as Facebook, WhatsApp and Instagram.

Students are the most important users of different social networks, such as learning programs designed for e-learning, virtual learning, or video learning. Excessive use of such networks will lead to reduced academic performance, because one will not want to survive in studies without the programs or software as references.

The addiction to social networks in business by Departments concerned with marketing can become extreme and lead to the loss of jobs for employees in strategic Departments that develop marketing policy. The addiction to using the social network for promotion or to carry out some marketing operations in the company that require excessive bureaucracy, can lead to a threat by sharing the company's secret documentation about its operations, perhaps to through hacking or mistakes made by employees.

As with other conditions that require a specialist for a solution, it is in the same way that social media addictions need therapy or a therapist, because it is a new situation that is greatly increasing worldwide in all the ages of humanity, and everything we do in society leads us to such addictions. Likewise, affected individuals can work closely with therapists concerned about social media addiction. Therapists can advise on a gradual decrease in addiction by using some programs such as video games. Apart from the therapist coming, the addict's family can also help warn of the bad results of social media addiction.

In society, we have to realize the effects that addiction has on our daily lives, from affecting the physical and psychological state of our body. Restricting or limiting the use of our phones can greatly help us reduce the negative effects of addiction.

Screen addiction, mobile phone addiction.

For the 5th and latest edition of the DMS (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) of the American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013) published in 2013, excessive use of mobile devices and exposure to screens in general do not represent a health problem. However, data from the latest study on the use of new technologies by the survey company Sonda reveals that Spaniards spend an average of 11 hours a day in front of a device with a screen (S/A ABC, 2019) and in Recent years have seen an alarming increase in psychological disorders related to addiction and excessive use of digital technologies.

According to Celso Arango, vice president of the Spanish Society of Psychiatry, noted in Torres Menárquez (2019), he states the following: “the diagnosis of new diseases always lags behind social changes [...] at the Gregorio Marañón Hospital in Madrid, the “Video game addiction is the second most treated addiction behind cannabis in adolescents.” We also know that one of the most demanding online activities is the use of social networks, that one in four 10-year-old children has a mobile phone (Pantaleoni, 2019) and that, despite the fact that almost 90% of Spaniards believe that

the indiscriminate use of the Internet undermines face-to-face relationships; one in three people looks at their cell phone more than 100 times a day (Fernández, 2019).

But how many hours in front of a screen are “too many”? As mobile applications and devices are a phenomenon in continuous evolution, are we facing an unknown paradigm with changing numbers? Are we generating more “tolerance” to the screen as the years go by, to the point that what seems “normal” to us today was too much before and will be too little later?

One of the most problematic aspects about the use and abuse of social networks is that we still do not have enough distance to understand the true effects of the number of hours we spend online. The most vulnerable population is the youngest and the relationship between children and technology is very difficult to analyze, because the accelerated pace at which it is transformed makes it difficult to reflect and study.

On the one hand, the generations that were born with the Internet have demonstrated greater skill in technological matters and seem to learn faster than previous generations; On the other hand, today we do not know what the consequences will be of children's exposure or over-exposure to cell phones and other interactive devices.

Without going any further, in Palo Alto, California, the executives of Google, Apple and other giants, “gurus” of digital technology, have decided that their children study in schools where screens are prohibited in primary education. This is the case of Waldorf of Peninsula, a private school in San Francisco Bay, which not only does not allow the use of cell phones and tablets, but also computers and televisions, nothing in the classrooms comes from a printer, and even the Textbooks are made by children with their own hands (Guimón, 2019). The uncertainty about the future psychological health of new generations has led those most knowledgeable in new technologies to consider that the possible benefits of screens in education are limited, when compared to the high risk of future addictions. For computer scientist Pierre Laurent, father of three children and president of the Waldorf board of trustees, he states the following:

If you put a screen on a small child, you limit their motor skills, their tendency to expand, their ability to concentrate. There are not many certainties in all this. We will have the answers in 15 years, when these children are adults. But do we want to take the risk? (Guimon, 2019).

There is still much to discover about the effect of new technologies on our lives and, just as it is possible that the use of computers and touch screens at an early age helps to form new skills aimed at needs that do not yet exist, it is also possible that exposure is already, in fact, limiting children's motor skills. And for many parents, this whole issue of future skills is unimportant when today they see their children lose control and suffer because they can't stop. According to a survey by the National Plan on Drugs of the Ministry of Health, in Spain 21% of young people between 10 and 25 years old suffer

from behavioral disorders due to technology (Torres Menárguez, 2019). Irrascibility, withdrawal syndrome, eating disorders, sleep disorders: these are some of the visible aspects of addiction to mobile devices, and according to the WHO, one of the symptoms of addiction is the progressive abandonment of interests other than the consumption of the “substance” or, in this case, that of immersion in the digital world. In other words, the need to be continually hyperconnected is, paradoxically, isolating technology addicts. The psychologist Encarnación Puertas from the Séfode of Cáceres psychology office affirms:

We observe that many teenagers feel bad when they do not attend to the messages that constantly arrive on their devices and are not able to wait to look at them. They need to be hyperconnected and that is known as FOMO, the English acronym for “fear of missing out”, which means fear of missing out on something (Rubio, 2019).

A question we may need to ask ourselves today is, “where” we are when we are with others. The online connection with other people and the experience of “inhabiting” a digital environment is not necessarily less real than relationships with, for example, the neighbors of a building whom we only cross casually. For the tech-savvy person who has also learned to combine and cross “on-line” relationships with “off-line” people, instant messaging, the possibility of immediately sharing photos and live videos, are a way to create links and maintain a level of continued intimacy that would be very difficult, if not impossible, by other means. Likewise, streaming events and what “is happening” on social networks are things that are actually happening, multilateral meetings between people connecting at the same time in a virtual space.

The problem with hyperconnectivity is that new communication tools offer enormous potential, perhaps too great for the average person to use. Wanting to know what is happening in our environment is normal and healthy. But that we become obsessed with knowing everything “what happens” in a virtual environment with billions of people connecting at the same time, sharing content from different platforms and managing transmedia experiences, is complete madness. According to the 2019 Annual Social Network Study, carried out by IAB Spain, Spain has more than 25 million social network users and the most used of all is WhatsApp with 88%; Of that 88% (22 million), 95% belong to at least one group and a third have 5 to 10 groups. Being aware of what is happening in, say, 7 groups and maintaining continuous Communication with an agenda of, say, 15 people, can be a highly stressful experience that, if combined with FOMO, fear of missing out, which sometimes Sometimes it is a terrifying anxiety where one is losing something absolutely fantastic, that feeling that others are having a wonderful and rewarding experience of which we are not a part (Bosker, 2011; Gregory & Rutledge, 2016), and it can trigger compulsive disorders and addiction. It's not just

about not picking up your cell phone every time the bell or terminal signal rings, it's about feeling like you're neglecting your own communities, just at the moments when “something is happening” to them.

However, it is important to note that not all excessive or indiscriminate use is considered an addiction. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), “an addiction is a physical and psycho-emotional disease that creates a need or dependence” towards what, in the case of social networks and mobile devices, is not a substance, but something intermediate between a type of activity and a form of relationship (WHO, 2008). In youth addiction to social media or online games, abusive dependency is usually accompanied by other problems such as school failure, withdrawal and social difficulties with people present in the flesh. In fact, according to psychologist Encarnación Puertas from the Séfode of Cáceres office, parents take their children to therapy when “there is another aspect to deal with, that is, when, for example, our child fails, does not pay attention or has difficulty socializing” (Rubio, 2019).

The fact that we need unwanted side effects to realize that there is a problem reveals how complex the issue is and how difficult it is to detect this type of addiction. On the other hand, in many cases, what at first glance seems like a side effect could be the cause of people immersing themselves in the virtual world. It is what Puertas calls a “dysfunctional coping with emotions” that leads us to take refuge in technology, in order to escape unpleasant situations such as stress, fear and anxiety. For José Moreno, director of the Center for Technological Addictions of the Community of Madrid:

If they take refuge in technology it is for a reason. It is what we call the iceberg phenomenon: addiction is what we see, but underneath there may be family conflicts, bullying, mourning the death of a loved one or changing country (Torres Menárguez, 2019).

In addition to treating underlying problems, experts recommend promoting proper use of devices, limiting screen time, and finding moments of enjoyment outdoors. Without completely removing the mobile phone from daily life, we can, for example, create screen-free areas or moments, such as the bedroom and meals. However, this issue of teaching responsible and balanced use of devices reveals another problem. Until recently, access to the internet, and even more so to mobile devices, was restricted to the population with better economic income. In 2011, only 52% of households with children had internet access. Currently, it is 98% (Guimón, 2019). With this massification of Internet access, the demographic problem has been reversed: families with higher incomes have more and better tools to prevent their children from being “raised by screens”:

Teenagers from lower-income households, according to a Common Sense Media study, spend two hours and 45 minutes a day more in front of screens than those from high-income households. Other studies indicate that white children are significantly less exposed to screens than black or Hispanic children (Guimón, 2019).

In short, with mobile terminals and their Applications, users exchange likes on Instagram, WhatsApp messages and Twitter memes.

Applied case studies.

The mobile phone comes with us everywhere, it is like another limb of our body, it seems like our friend, but sometimes it is not such a good friend, let's see it in a Sociological Observation study, carried out by Sara Fernández Gómez¹ in 2022 in the city of Cáceres, but it is a faithful reflection of what happens on any street in our city. In it you can see that the use of the mobile phone is an epidemic that is spreading in each of the areas of our lives, although it has been a great advance for some of these areas, for others it may not be so much.

We are talking about the field of driving, how many people use their phone while driving? Therefore, this study deals with this phenomenon, the use of mobile phones while driving. The idea arose when the author of said study, walking through the city one day, saw a pedestrian standing at a traffic light and talking animatedly through her mobile phone. Even though this is a serious infraction, many of us use the telephone while our lives, or those of people close to us, are in danger. We have internalized it so much that we not only make calls, but also allow ourselves the luxury of sending messages, watching a YouTube video, or even watching a series.

Summarizing this work, it was possible to verify between the two moments of observation that several drivers, mostly men between the ages of 35-45, are the ones who use their mobile phone the most.

All the drivers observed used their mobile phones to talk, and none of them to send messages, something surprising. Also, note that the majority used mobile phones and were unaccompanied.

And finally, it should be noted that more than the drivers used the phone, it was used by the pedestrians who crossed the pedestrian crossing, as in the study we saw previously on the use of the mobile phone at the pedestrian crossing, making a complete use of their phone, since they talked, listened to music or even exchanged instant messages.

¹ student of the Master's Degree in Teacher Training in Secondary Education (Socio-community Intervention) at the University of Extremadura (Spain), during the 22/23 Academic Year.

This represents a true suicidal act, since if a driver is careless, the result of a maneuver is left in his hands.

This study can be contrasted with the VI Distraction Report of the Royal Automobile Club of Spain (RACE -Department of Communication-, 2019. p 2-24), which reveals worrying data and information regarding road safety, it is based on:

"The exponential increase in dangerous attitudes in traffic related to the use of mobile phones." This report was based on an online interview (between May 27 and June 4, 2018) with a total of 2,132 users between 18 and 65 years of age and from 17 Autonomous Communities. According to this survey, 96% confessed to having seen someone talking on their cell phone while driving (80% regularly), and 76% using their cell phone without talking (handling it or looking at it).

According to this survey, carried out among more than 2,100 users, using the mobile phone while driving is one of the most repeated tasks performed by the driver. 96% of those surveyed state and acknowledge having seen someone talking on their mobile phone while driving (80% on a regular basis), and 76% acknowledge using the mobile terminal only to manipulate and/or observe it.

The use of mobile phones, driving and traffic have provided new data regarding the problems posed by this VI Report. Spaniards were asked about certain habits of mobile phone use as drivers and pedestrians, in situations related to circulation, reaching the conclusion that the use and abuse of the mobile phone has been the cause of accidents, accidents and deaths in our cities.

Therefore, we will have to ask ourselves the following questions: Are we aware of the danger to which we expose ourselves with these situations? Do we voluntarily put other pedestrians or people at risk? Is it just a problem for drivers?

Based on a Sociological Observation study carried out by Virginia Castaño, Sheila del Valle Vaca Matamoros and Jennifer Blanco Correa², carried out in 2021, in the classroom of a Secondary Education Institute, in the 1st year of Baccalaureate class with a student body of 25 people between the ages of 15 and 16, it was observed that first thing in the morning the cell phone is hardly used, as opposed to the last hour. It should also be noted that depending on the subjects, mobile phone use increases, as in Language and History.

To conclude, let's say that, although using the cell phone in class is prohibited, we can verify with this observation that it is used and in most cases without consequences.

² students of the Master's Degree in Teacher Training in Secondary Education (Socio-community Intervention) of the University of Extremadura (Spain), during the 20/21 Academic Year,

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The use of the mobile phone in class can cause the student to become distracted and easily lose concentration, for this reason I think that the mobile phone should be integrated as another learning tool in the classrooms.

The students referenced above, in said Sociological Observation study, point out that: "We must begin to accept that the mobile phone is an essential part of the students' lives, and the problem is not the tool itself, it is how we use it." For this reason, it is necessary to make the most of new technologies, and use it, for example, to search for information, know how to navigate the Internet to find interesting content, etc.

In parallel, in the same study, the use of mobile phones is analyzed among 1st year Baccalaureate students of a Secondary Education Institute, during the rest period, that is, during recess. Recesses should be spaces where the connection with children is encouraged, the stimulation of the imagination and, above all, interaction and symbolic play. Recess is a space where students go out to enjoy some time for themselves, it is an opportunity to develop social skills and for them to establish social relationships with their classmates, that is, it is a great pillar to promote socialization.

But according to what has been observed, the vast majority of students, if not all, cannot spend recess without looking at their mobile phone once. But this is not the most serious thing, but rather that half of the recess or a little more they are glued to their mobile phones. Some even isolate themselves for most of recess and don't even interact with their peers. Therefore, one might think that some of these students showed addictive behavior when using the mobile phone, since they even used the mobile phone to socialize with their classmates. Regarding this, there is a phenomenon called phubbing and which consists of ignoring the people around us, with whom we could have a conversation and pay more attention to our cell phone, so instead of socializing with people that we have at that moment next to us, we do it with those who are on the other side of the device. This is seen a lot in teenagers during recess, there were some who spoke to the classmate who was on the phone and he did not even answer them. It is clear that the mobile phone is already part of young people today, but the misuse they can make and the abusive use of it should be controlled. In some cases, minors do not have a telephone addiction but overuse, but it is necessary that, both in schools and at home, they control the possible risk of it becoming an addiction.

Furthermore, during school hours and in the different classrooms, the use of mobile phones is controlled and supervised, and in some institutes their use is even prohibited in the building, even during class changes. But, on the other hand, the use of the mobile phone is not controlled or supervised during breaks, so this can encourage compulsive use of the mobile phone, since during the rest of the hours they have not been able to consult their phones.

This compulsive use of mobile phones can cause significant dependency problems of which educators cannot be immune, since the consequences can be very dangerous for minors. We cannot deny the reality or the dangers to which minors are exposed and of which they are not aware due to misuse of the mobile phone.

To analyze the phenomenon of addiction to the use of Social Networks, we take as reference a Sociological Observation (Self-observation) study carried out by Tomás Pineda Rodríguez³ in the city of Cáceres (Spain) in 2022, and where dependence on the mobile phone was examined during the teaching schedule at the university.

To carry out this study, the student has been writing down from Monday to Thursday (last week of October 2022), all the times he started an application once he had unlocked the mobile terminal, but only when the teacher was teaching class. If while the teacher was in the classroom teaching, he looked at his cell phone, he had to write it down. Once he had finished the class he did not make any registration until the next class began.

To collect the data, he has created a table from Monday to Thursday, putting the 3 daily subjects on each day and in each subject adding a section for the 4 applications that he frequently uses on his smartphone: WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter and Others. The Others section includes applications such as checking email, checking Google, checking how much time is left on the bus or simply playing a phone game.

Once the data is obtained, a line graph is made to see the times that the student accesses the mobile phone during those 4 days, in the different subjects.

From the data obtained, this graph (figure 1) shows the number of times the student starts all the applications each day of the week. The objective is to see the evolution for days in your "technoaddiction".

Figure 1. Number of times the student starts all applications each day of the week.

³ student of the Degree in Criminology and Law at the University of Extremadura, during the 22/23 Academic Year.

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Note: Tomás Pineda Rodríguez, 2022.

As can be seen, from Monday to Wednesday there is a progressive evolution in the number of starts, reaching a maximum point of 38 on Wednesday. Subsequently, there is a drop of more than 22% from Wednesday to Thursday. This graph shows that as the week progresses, the student uses and accesses the mobile phone more during class time.

And in this graph (figure 2) he wanted to reflect the times he uses and accesses the mobile phone the most during class hours and classified by day.

Figure 2. Number of times the student uses and accesses the mobile phone during class time, and classified by day.

Note: Tomás Pineda Rodríguez, 2022.

As you can see, the most used application by difference is WhatsApp, followed by Instagram; Then there would be other types of applications and, finally, we find Twitter. You can also see what is explained in the previous graph: the blue bar, which corresponds to Wednesday where the different applications were started 38 times, is overall the most numerous because it dominates both WhatsApp and Twitter and is the second on Instagram . The purple bar (which corresponds to Tuesday with 31 starts) and the green bar (which represents Thursday with 30 starts) although it represents more or less the same starts (31 to 30), the purple one dominates Instagram and Twitter more and the green in the other applications. The orange bar which represents Monday with 27 starts has a much shorter length with the rest practically in the 4 applications.

From this graph it can be seen that the student is more trapped in Communication than in entertainment, hence the messaging applications such as WhatsApp and Instagram, which although it is an application to share photos and "gossip" to the people around them He also has his own messaging service, which he uses quite frequently, that is; He does not use the mobile phone as a mere object of entertainment in class but as an instrument of Communication, to constantly be in contact with family and friends.

The student shows that having non-serious conversations through messages on applications such as WhatsApp and Instagram has become a real vice, especially among younger people like him.

Figure 3. Number of times the student has used the different applications in the 6 subjects taken.

Note: Tomás Pineda Rodríguez, 2022.

This last graph (figure 3) shows us the times that the student has used the different applications in the 6 subjects taken. It shows perfectly in which subjects you are most entertained or most busy and interested in responding to a message or looking at some news or photograph.

If the objective of this study was to confirm mobile phone addiction, it has been achieved because a clear and high dependence of the student on the mobile terminal is demonstrated. But in addition, we have managed to see that mobile addiction is rather an addiction to Communication via messages rather than an addiction to virtual entertainment (games, photos, videos, gossip, etc.). And without a doubt, the applications that I used the most were the applications that had a messaging service such as WhatsApp and Instagram.

The student Tomás Pineda Rodríguez, as a conclusion and summary in the Sociological Self-observation study, in 2022, highlights the following:

“Even so, without a doubt, in class I do not use my cell phone as much as I abuse it, and seeing all this I have to start considering leaving it in airplane mode, turning it off or putting it in my backpack in order to avoid falling into temptation and starting a "telephone detox" process”.

The student believes that it is a serious problem, not only in his case, but also that of more and more adolescents, who find it difficult or simply cannot separate themselves from their smartphones. He states that they live with a complete addiction to the digital world and when they are deprived of it, they act like junkies, or what he also calls: "technological junkies." It is evident that serious measures must begin to be taken regarding this, but the first ones who must have the will to change have to be themselves, the protagonists of this issue.

The student admits that he is a person who is quite attached to his mobile phone, and needs to constantly look at it. Any moment, no matter how small, is a good time to take a look at the mobile terminal, even if you have not received any notifications. And not only the moment, but also any place is good to do it, whether on the couch, in bed, on the bus or even in class.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, social networks are widely used and play an important role in our daily lives, they bring closeness and connectivity in society, but then, they are being used excessively by a sector of people in society, and this leads to addiction to its use; Addiction brings some impacts on users in positive and negative ways. People tend to abuse different networks for some reasons that seem right to them, and those are the causes of social media addiction. Some people will want to improve their lifestyle, others in the community will want to use it for educational purposes and also for business. Addiction brings negative disorders to our health, affects our job performance and obtaining those jobs, and again reduces student performance. Victims sometimes feel overwhelmed and need physical or psychological help, and this can be done well by the victim's family members and a therapist in the social media addictions category.

Social networks have an impact that is still too early to measure, even when we can see from a distance what is happening today, technological advances, changes in the ways of communicating will have influenced society in such a way that it will probably We will have other concerns.

Knowing whether the use of social networks causes depression or conditions acceptance, not only of the environment but of ourselves, is something that we will be able to see over time. The situation becomes more complex when we can see that the

use of social networks is not limited only to young people, although we can assume that the effects on them will be different than on older people.

Determining when use is excessive, when it has become an addiction, represents another difficulty. What some may consider an abuse of electronic devices and presence on social networks, for others may be a fair and even insufficient use, especially if we consider some elements that would be the subject of another type of essay, such as the use of social networks and communication technologies in education and in awareness campaigns on health, gender equality, violence and security. It would even be worth considering sociologically what is considered private life in a world in which the majority is constantly sending information about what they do, what they have, what they want and with whom. Likewise, what is the consideration of people who have accounts on social networks but who browse only to “spy” on others, who never publish anything, but who check their accounts to see what others have posted. The world of social networks is complex, and we have not even begun to see its consequences and influences in today's world.

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